

Exploring the impact of applying iPod application in promoting learner's speaking skill: A Case Study of EFL Students at the International School, Khartoum, Sudan (2022)

¹Mariam Ahmed Omran Elbashir, ²Dr. Tahiya Alshaikh Al hameem,
³Dr. Montasir Hassan Mubarak

¹PhD. Student .Sudan University of Science and Technology, College of Education. English Language.

²Alzaiem Alazhri University College of Education, English

³Sudan University of science and Technology College of Education. English Language.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10410756>

Published Date: 20-December-2023

Abstract: Speaking seems to be the most important skill of all the four skills. This study aims at investigating the impact of using iPods and other smart devices on EFL learners' speaking skills and showing the motivational role of using iPods technology in EFL teaching and learning. The study adopted the descriptive analytical method. The data for the study is collected by means of a questionnaire which was distributed among twenty four students of the international schools in Khartoum (2020), and then the collected data were analyzed by the SPSS program. The study findings are : using iPod technology in EFL classes learning enables students to participate in speaking activity, using smart devices generates students' motivation to speak in English , the application of iPod technology in EFL classes is better than the uses of other regular communicative method. The study recommends: EFL learners should be enabled to improve their performance of speaking through using iPods technology, EFL learners should be motivated through using iPod technology in learning English language and EFL teachers should be trained on using iPods in teaching the language skills.

Keywords: The application of iPods technology, speaking skills, students' motivation, using smart devices in learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, mastering speaking skills in English is very important for education and global communication. The use of modern learning tools that support effective English learning is critical issue in English language education (Chen and Chung, 2008). It is believed that iPods and smart devices are not only able to support formal and informal learning but also complete the process of learning via computers. The use of iPod in EFL teaching helps students to develop an understanding of various aspects of pedagogy in the classroom context, primarily relating to the areas of student engagement, speaking in group work, and selection of materials in the form of apps (Pegrum , et, 2013)

1.1 problem statement

Many EFL students face difficulties in speaking whenever they are put in real life situations. The researchers think that this problem might be due the fact that English is at most taught traditionally and artificially without using any technology that gives students a chance to acquire authentic English in real life situations.

1.2 Objectives

The study aims at:

1. Investigating the impact of using iPod applications on EFL learners' speaking skills.
2. Showing the motivational role of using iPods technology in EFL teaching.

1.3 Questions of the study

The study will answer the following questions:

1. What is the impact of using iPod technology on EFL learners' speaking skills?
2. To what extent does the application of iPod technology motivate EFL learners to learn English by using iPod in learning?

1.4 Hypotheses of the study:

1. iPod application in EFL classes has appositive impact on learners' speaking skills.
2. The application of iPods technology motivates EFL learners to learn English language accurately.

1.5 Significance of the study:

The study is useful for EFL teachers, learners and as syllabus designers as the effectiveness of using iPods technology in teaching speaking skills in EFL classes. The findings of the research may help teachers to examine the feasibility of using technology as a supplement in teaching and learning English language.

1.6 Methodology of the study:

The study adopted the descriptive method. The population of this research is EFL teachers and students in Khartoum, Sudan (2022).The sample of the study are twenty four EFL students who will be randomly selected from the general population of the study. A questionnaire will be used for data collection. Then the collected data will be analyzed with SPSS program.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Limited opportunities to use the English language in conversations contributes to low confidence levels in L2 learners about communicating in the target language.(Barlow , Wisessuwan and Tubsree 2014). The learners avoid making mistakes when interacting in the target language .thus creating inactive English language learning classrooms due to limited participation from the learners.(Barlow2005).Labels iPods learning as an extension of e-learning and accomplishing the learning using small and portable devices. According TO (Ally, 2009) , smart devices learning through the use of technology allows students to access information and learning materials l.(Pegurm et . al. 2013) argues that the pre-service teachers' comments on the pedagogical impact of iPod in their own teaching show that many of them had reflected on at least some key areas, such as engagement , group work, and materials. But explicit direction by lecturers might encourage more students to reflect on more themes related to best practice in the use of technology in the classroom.

More obviously, the use of iPod as a technology tool that fostered new learning opportunities for teachers of special with disabilities and for students themselves, the feeling from each teacher was device's flexibility made the prospect of trying new things easier and more manageable. iPod provides further opportunities for students to interact with each other and participate in classroom activities. According to (Baig, 2013) , iPod and its applications can be used to enhance different texts being read in the classroom, provide resources for understanding, the material further or for extending and assessing reading comprehension. Also iPod is used to access e-books, which will provide students with a multimodal reading experience that will engage them with animation and sound.

3. MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study adopted the descriptive analytical method. The population of the study was EFL secondary school teachers Khartoum. The participants of this study were twenty four of EFL learners at the international schools in Khartoum, Sudan,(2022).

They were selected randomly from the population of the study. The collected data was statistically analyzed with the SPSS program.

4. DATA ANALYSES AND DISCUSSION:

Statement (1) using iPod technology in EFL learning enables students to participate in speaking activity.

Table (1) Enabling students to participate in speaking activity

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neutral	1	4.2	4.2	4.2
	Agree	10	41.7	41.7	45.8
	Strongly agree	13	54.2	54.2	100.0
	Total	24	100.0	100.0	

Fig(1) Enable students to participate in speaking activity

The data in table (1) shows that most respondents, (54.1) strongly agree, (41.5%) agree that using iPod technology in EFL learning enables students to participate in speaking activity. Only (4.2) of the sample are neutral. Therefore, this statement is justified.

Statement (2) by using iPod applications, students may get rid of fear and shyness.

Table (2) students may get rid of fear and shyness by using iPod.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	3	12.5	12.5	12.5
	Neutral	3	12.5	12.5	25.0
	Agree	15	62.5	62.5	87.5
	Strongly agree	3	12.5	12.5	100.0
	Total	24	100.0	100.0	

Fig (2) students may get rid of fear and shyness by using iPods

The statistical results in table (2) show that (12.4) of the sample strongly agree, (62.5%) agree ,(12%) of the sample disagree that using iPod applications , students may get rid of fear and shyness . Thus this statement is approved.

Statement (3) Using smart devices in EFL classes increase students’ motivation to speak in English fluently.

Table (3) Increasing students’ motivation to speak English fluently.

SM3

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Disagree	3	12.5	12.5	12.5
Neutral	1	4.2	4.2	16.7
Agree	10	41.7	41.7	58.3
Strongly agree	10	41.7	41.7	100.0
Total	24	100.0	100.0	

Fig (3) . Increasing students’ motivation to speak in English.

The statistical results in table and fig, (3) show that (41.7) of he sample strongly agree, (41.6) agree (4.2%) of sample are neutral and (12.4%) disagree that using smart devices in EFL classes increase students motivation to speak in English. The statement is proved.

Statement (4) . Students need to be engouraged to speak bravely to promote their speaking by using ipod application in classroom.

Table (4) .Promoting students' speaking by using ipod technology in classroom.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Disagree	2	8.3	8.3	8.3
Neutral	4	16.7	16.7	25.0
Agree	5	20.8	20.8	45.8
Strongly agree	13	54.2	54.2	100.0
Total	24	100.0	100.0	

Fig(4) Promoting student' speaking by using iPod technology in classroom.

According to the statistical analysis, in the table and fig (4) (55.1%) of ht sample strongly agree, (20.75%) of them agree, (16.7%) of the sample are neutral and (8.3%) of them disagree that student need to be encouraged to speak bravely to promote their speaking by using iPod in learning. Accordingly this statement is justified.

Statement (5) .The application of iPod technology in EFL classes is better than the uses of other regular communicative method.

Table (5) the application of iPod technology in EFL learning.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Disagree	2	8.3	8.3	8.3
Agree	11	45.8	45.8	54.2
Strongly agree	11	45.8	45.8	100.0
Total	24	100.0	100.0	

Fig (5) the application of iPod technology in EFL classes

The data in table and fig (5) explain that (45.7) of the sample agree. (45.65%) of them strongly agree and (8.3%) of the sample are neutral .The iPod technology in EFL classes is better that the uses of other traditional communicative method.

Statement (6) the using iPod can motivates students towards positive foreign language learning and creates a relaxed atmosphere in the classroom.

Table (6) motivating students towards positive foreign language learning.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Neutral	6	25.0	25.0	25.0
Agree	5	20.8	20.8	45.8
Strongly agree	13	54.2	54.2	100.0
Total	24	100.0	100.0	

Fig (6) motivating students towards positive foreign language learning.

The statistical results in table and fig (6) show that (54.2 %) of the sample strongly agree, (20.8%) of them agree and (25%) of them are neutral that the use of IPod applications motivates students towards positive foreign language learning and creates a relaxed atmosphere in the classroom. Therefore, this statement is proved.

Statement (7) Using IPods facilitate the teacher's job by changing his role from a manager to a facilitator.

Table (7) Changing teacher's role from a manager to a facilitator.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	1	4.2	4.2	4.2
	Neutral	8	33.3	33.3	37.5
	Agree	9	37.5	37.5	75.0
	Strongly agree	6	25.0	25.0	100.0
	Total	24	100.0	100.0	

Fig (7) Changing teacher's role from a manager to a facilitator..

The statistical results in table and fig (7) show that, (25 %) of the sample strongly agree, (37.5 %) of them agree,(33.3%) of the sample are neutral and (4.2%) of them disagree that using IPods facilitate the teacher's job by changing his role from a manager to a facilitator. Thus, the statement is justified.

Statement (8) EFL teachers should encourage students to perform speaking activities in pair work by using IPod application in classroom.

Table (8) Encouraging students to perform speaking activities in pair work

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	1	4.2	4.2	4.2
	Neutral	5	20.8	20.8	25.0
	Agree	9	37.5	37.5	62.5
	Strongly agree	9	37.5	37.5	100.0
	Total	24	100.0	100.0	

Fig (8) Encouraging students to perform speaking activities in pair work

The analysis of the data in table and fig (8) Shows that (37.5 %) of the sample strongly agree and (37.5%) of them agree,(20.8%) are neutral and (4.2%) disagree that EFL teachers should encourage students to perform speaking activities in pair work by using iPod application in classroom. Accordingly, this statement is accepted.

Statement (9) Educators who use iPods technology in their teaching are flexible and fast achievers of their lesson objectives

Table (9) Educators who use iPods technology are flexible and fast achievers

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Neutral	3	12.5	12.5	12.5
Agree	9	37.5	37.5	50.0
Strongly agree	12	50.0	50.0	100.0
Total	24	100.0	100.0	

Fig (9) Educators who use iPods tools are flexible and fast achievers

The statistical analysis of the data in table and fig (9) explains that (50 %) of the sample strongly agree, (37.5%) agree and (12.5%) of the sample are neutral that educators who use iPods tools are flexible and fast achievers of their lesson objectives. Accordingly, the statement is justified.

Statement (10) In the traditional Learning the teacher is the primary source of information. By contrast the use of technology shifts the mode to web-based resources.

Table (10) Using technology shifts the mode to web-based resources.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	1	4.2	4.2	4.2
	Neutral	2	8.3	8.3	12.5
	Agree	11	45.8	45.8	58.3
	Strongly agree	10	41.7	41.7	100.0
	Total	24	100.0	100.0	

Fig (10) Using technology shifts the mode to web-based resources.

According to the data in table and fig.(10), (41.7%) of the sample strongly agree, (45.8%) of them agree, (8.3%) of them are neutral and (4.2%) of the sample disagree that in the traditional learning the teacher is the primary source of information. By contrast using technology shifts the mode to a web-based resources..The statement is justified.

5. FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Findings

After data analysis, the study came out with the following findings:

1. Using iPod technology in EFL learning enables students to participate in speaking activity
2. By using iPod applications, students may get rid of fear and shyness
3. Smart devices help student's motivation to speak in English.
4. Students need to be encouraged to speak bravely to promote their speaking by using iPods application in classroom.
5. The application of iPod technology in EFL classes is better than the uses of other regular communicative method
6. The use of iPod applications motivates students towards positive foreign language learning and creates a relaxed atmosphere in the classroom.

7. Using iPods facilitate the teacher's job by changing his role from a manager to a facilitator.
8. EFL teachers should encourage students to perform speaking activities in pair work by using iPod application in classroom.

5.2 Recommendations.

Based on the previous findings, the study recommends:

- 1- Further similar studies for other classes can be conducted in order to make the results more valid and more widely applicable.
- 2- Learners should be enabled to improve their speaking skills through iPod applications.
3. Smart devices should be applied in EFL teaching to motivate students.
4. Students should be encouraged to speak bravely to promote their speaking.
5. Teachers should be trained on how to use iPod technology in teaching the language skills.
- 6- Ministry of Education can activate the role of iPod applications and adopt them in its curricula.
- 7- The Ministry of Education should train teachers by giving workshops on using iPod applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ally, M. (2009). *Mobile learning: Transforming the delivery of education and training*. Athabasca: AU Press.
- [2] Baig, I. (2013) Examining the Impact Information Communication Technology (ICT) Has on Adolescents with Disabilities: *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, Vol. 3, No. 6, December 2013.
- [3] Barlow, D. M., Wisessuwan, A., & Tubsree, C. (2014). Design of an English speaking skills development course for second language learners. *HRD Journal*, 4(2):73-81.
- [4] Brown, T. H (2005). Towards a model for m-learning in Africa. *International Journal of E-learning*, 4(3), 299-315.
- [5] Chen, Ch.-M., & Chung, Ch.-J. (2008). Personalized mobile English vocabulary learning system based on item-response theory and learning memory cycle. *Journal of Computer and Education*, 51 (2), 624-645
- [6] Pegrum, M. , Howitt, CH, & Striepe, M. (2013) Learning to take the tablet: How pre-service teachers use iPodsto facilitate their learning: *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 2013, 29(4).